

CRACK RESISTANCE OF STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS OF AL-B COMPOSITE UNDER TENSION

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ABSTRACT

Evaluation of crack resistance of carrying elements of Al-B composite includes calculation of loading level of tube elements by finite elements method (FEM); structural imitation modelling of fracture processes of unidirectional composites; elaboration of methods of non-destructive control of the constructions; crack resistance testing of specimens and structural elements; use of crack resistance characteristics for evaluation of fracture probability. High values of the strength and crack resistance characteristics of the composites are realized due to their capability of the strength reservation. The experimental results allow to evaluate the sizes of critical defects, probability indices of faultless work of the construction.

Keywords: brittle fibres, crack resistance, unidirectional composite, size effect

1 INTRODUCTION

Unique technologies of production and exploitation of the material and the structure elements, high cost of the material and the space vehicles demand for complex investigation of composite hardware. The high strength of the brittle fibres is accompanied by wide scatter of critical stresses with coefficient of variation from 10 to 40 %. The material has initial heterogeneities — the broken fibres, irregularity of the fibre stacking. Bond between the plastic spraying matrix and the fibre are sufficiently irregular and have local exfoliations. Production does not exclude the presence of macroscopic defects — the cracks. The material with defects has high resistance to fracture owing to redistribution of the loads from damage zones to the adjoining areas. There is sufficient difference in characteristics of the composite strength obtained at small specimens and full-scale elements of construction. The material has specific character of fracture, which essentially differ at static and cyclic loading. In the paper the results of complex investigation lead to a high degree of safety of composite tube elements are presented.

2 LOADING OF THE COMPOSITE

The design cases take account of the assembly stresses, the overloads in the process of satellite launching, cyclic loading in orbit as a result of changes of thermal effect and etc. The results of calculations of three-dimensional (3D) FEM problems and modelling experiments are the limit static load under tension P_t and compression P_c , characteristics of the cyclic loading –

maximal load of the tube element P_{max} , stress ratio R and required service life (number of cycles N).

The tube element of construction consists of the composite tube and two bimetallic end parts. To provide estimation of overload level in the end part of the tube calculations were carried out by 3D FEM program 'Strength and Durability Prediction' [1]. Shown in Figure 1 the deformed FE mesh illustrates the character of the deformation under tension (the displacements increased in 400 were added to nodes coordinates). The dark zones show higher than average stress level. Analogous calculations were carried out for cases with the presence of delaminations in the end part and for different types of loading — tension, bending, torsion. In all these cases the overload levels in composite material were not more than 20 %.

Figure 1. Deformed mesh of the tube

3 THE COMPOSITE FRACTURE MODELLING

Models of the composite structure of different scales [2-5] allow to evaluate the deformation, strength parameters of the composition by the components properties. Thus in model [4] the overloads at certain distance from broken fibre are directly calculated by numerical methods from the solution of the problem of stress-strain state in the concrete damaged structure. Among basic regularities of strength of the unidirectional composite with brittle fibres revealed in numerical modelling are effects of strength reservation in presence of the microflaws, determining role of the fibre strength scatter and energy-intensity of the plastic matrix, influences of the volume fraction and structure inhomogenities (unproportional stacking, initial microflaws, edge defects and etc.) on the mechanisms and parameters of the material fracture, the size effect, resistance to the macrocrack growth and others.

For the composite with brittle fibres and plastic matrix there was created the special FE model (Fig. 2) with matrix elements working in shear and tension and tensile fibre elements. The total model includes about 30000 FE. Nonlinear problem is solved by step-by-step method with increasing of nominal deformation. For each structural (finite) element the limit (critical) strain is defined with respect to accepted probability function, for example from plot of Figure 3 (the brittle fibre). It was observed breakage of the fibres, local separation matrix and fibres even at initial stages of the loading, but these microdamages did not cause to making macrocrack — spontaneous fracture. Figure 4a shows one of the plies of the composite at the stage of final rupture, when microdamages rearrange to a macroscopic crack. Figure 4b displays the formation of the microdamages in the composite specimen with initial crack. The characteristic feature of the composite is the fact that final fracture of the material precedes with previous formation of the delaminations in the crack tip, which

may be as much as length of the tube (specimen). Analogous character of the fracture is observed in test of tubes with transverse crack (Figure 4c).

Figure 2. FE model of the composite

Figure 3. Size effect for fibre and composite

To evaluate the composite strength it is more convenient to use the magnitudes of critical (limit) strain. Going from critical stress to the strain is based on the fact that fracture of the composite takes place with different values of nominal critical stress in the fibres, matrix and composite, but at the same level of the strain in them. Another cause is the fact that if limit stresses of the composites with instable volume fraction may be sufficiently different, then the critical strains have more stable values. For Weibull distribution the strength characteristic plotted against total length of fibres L in the logarithmic coordinates is a straight line [6] with tangent of inclination angle equal $-1/\beta$ (Figure 3, dashed lines, $\beta = 12$). Critical strains are related to the average critical strain of the fibre of adopted length $0.1 M$. Boundaries of 99% confidence interval are also shown at the figure. Theoretical analysis [5] allows to construct analogous dependences for the composite material (Figure 3, solid lines). Critical strains of the composite with real total length of the fibres ($lg(L) \gg 0$) are less than the limit strain for short fibre ($0.1 M$), but greater than the strength parameter of the fibre with the same length L . According to the diagram the final fracture of the composite does not take place directly after first breakage of the fibres. The differences of the critical strains for a fibre and composite quantitatively characterize the effect of strength reservation. The loads are redistributed from damaged structural elements to the adjoining zones having greater carrying ability. It is possible to find an analogy with assemblage of series-parallel connections in the theory of reliability when failure of structural element causes transmission of the working functions to the adjacent elements. The strength scatter of the brittle fibre, ability of the composite structure to transform the load are decisive factors for the effect of strength reservation.

Consider a relationship between critical strain of the composites and its volume fraction v_f (Figure 5). The diagram is constructed on the by assuming that all parameters, except in v_f , including total length of the fibres, plastic properties of the matrix and the strength of the components interface are fixed. Critical strain of matrix is plotted at $v_f = 0$. With $v_f = 1.0$ it is difficult to mark the experimental data of the bundle of fibres test. It is possible to draw the data for short fibre or predict a common tendency. There are three characteristic sections

Figure 4. Results of modelling (a,b) and surface of Al-B specimen with crack(c)

Figure 5. Critical strain versus volume fraction for unidirectional composites

of the diagram : with dominant role of the matrix (“reinforced matrix”), a zone of exhibition of the composite properties (“composite material”), with predominance of the brittle fibres properties (“bundle of fibres”). These materials have principally different mechanisms of fracture. For section with dominant role of the matrix, the critical strain of the material depends on mechanical properties of the matrix with splintered fibres. For the second type of the material, the level of the stable critical strain is specified by scatter of the fibre strength and ability of the structure to redistribute the loads. For the third section, the minimal values of the brittle fibres strength and fibre-to-fibre bond are decisive factors.

4 NON-DESTRUCTIVE CONTROL

Reliable estimation of the crack resistance includes the systems of initial defect identification. The artificial flaws in the composite tube were burned out by the laser ray. The non-destructive control of the tubes were made before and after cyclic loading, which simulates vibro-test of the construction. Among known nondestructive methods [8], the preference

Figure 6. Damaged zones presented by radiograph, thermovision and holograph methods

were made to those methods which allow not only to analyse the signals but to view the images.

The radiograph method. The defect sizes were evaluated through local radiating of the film inside the tube by outside stationary source. The method exactly identifies the sizes of the through and surface defects perpendicular to the fibres. Identification of the delaminations by the method is difficult. The best results may be obtained if to compare two films - before and after vibrotesting. A typical picture in zone of initial defect with length $2a_0$ after cyclic loading is shown in Figure 6a. In the initial notch tip the fatigue crack with length da was grown.

Thermovision. The temperature gradient was created by heating one of the tube ends, and recorded by the termovisor AGA camera placed at the certain distance from the tube. Increase of the temperature is approximately 10 – 20 %. The method is efficient in identification of the through defects. Another way of the identification is the registration of thermal fields during cyclic tensile loading of the construction elements. In the test the difference of the temperature in the damage zones within 1 – 2 °C is registered. The method allows to find out the interlaminar defects.

Holographic interferometry. The exposures of the pictures of the tube while cooling after heating by the internal radiating source were made with interval 5 – 7 minutes. By the method both longitudinal and transverse defects were efficiently identified. After the cyclic loading the fatigue interlaminar defects were revealed. A fatigue crack in the composite tube and zone of possible delaminations between composite and bimetallic end part are clearly observed at the Figure 6c. The method is more efficient for investigation of inner delaminations in the end parts of the tube, where possibilities of other methods are restricted.

Efficient revealing of different types of defects including dangerous crack is possible only with complex using of set of non-destructive methods. Common conception of the non-destructive control of the composite tube structures consists in application at the first stage

Figure 7. Critical stresses for composite tubes and specimens

of diagnostics a mobil method with wide interval of scale (thermovision) in addition to visual control. The method may be applied directly in the vibrotesting procedures or structure assemblage. At the second stage of non-destructive evaluation another mentioned methods may be recommended.

5 CRACK RESISTANCE TESTING

Some of the AL-B composite tubes were cutted into specimens. Volume fraction of fibres in the material is equal to 43 %. Tensile testing of 8 specimens with sizes approximately $150 \times 7 \times 2$ mm give next results: average value of critical stress is equal to 957 MPa with coefficient of variation 20 % (Figure 7) and average value of critical strain is equal to 0.48 % with less coefficient of variation 12 %. At the surfaces of the tubes and specimens the sharp notches were made by the electro-erosive method (Figure 4c).

Figure 8 shows one of the parts of fractured tube with initial straight notch. There are delaminations in the notch tips, a sufficiently irregular fracture surface with local splits, stretching fibres, delaminations of the plies. The failure of the fibrous composite is a sequence of local fracture acts – delaminations, breakage of the fibres, its pulling out from the matrix, rupture of the matrix. During tension of the tubes it was heard a popping – result of sudden drop of the local rigity. After this the loading was continued and the tube fractured at greater load. Effect of “popping” is connected with internal changes in the composite structure – abrupt increasing of damages in the notch tip. After this, the damaged zone unloaded and its loads redistributed at the stronger fibres. The effect is not observed for specimens because of the less volumes of the material, where the stop of the crack is possible. Critical value of stress intensity factor was determined with “popping” load.

In the Figure 7 for different types of specimens and tubes the critical nominal stresses are plotted against crack length. The nominal stresses are determined as ratio of critical load to area of netto-section of the specimen (tube) exclusive of the crack. Values of stresses for $K_{IC} = 238 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{M}$ (average magnitude for 5 tubes) are shown by dashed line. A solid line shows dependence for two-parameter integral criterion with mentioned values K_{IC} and σ_c . Critical stresses obtained in tests of the specimens are higher than the curve, which

Figure 8. Fractured composite tube

characterizes crack resistance of the full-scale elements – the tubes. Nondestructive control shows that in the end part of the tube different types of inner defects may be found. In test of one of the tubes it was ruptured with initialization of crack from end part of the tube. By knowing the fracture stress and curve $K_{IC} = const$ it is possible to evaluate the size of conventional defect, from which the crack started.

For cyclic loading of the tube with initial defect, which is transverse to the fibres, it was observed a little growth of the crack in the notch plane and then the delaminations started from the crack tip. Figure 4c shows typical delaminations in the notch tip. From a plot of delamination length versus number of cycles, the parameters in the equation connected crack growth rate and value of stress intensity factor K_{II} in the tip if the delamination were found (Figure 9).

6 CALCULATION OF CRACK RESISTANCE INDICES

It is convenient to use data of Figure 7 in calculations of crack resistance indices for tensile composite tube with transverse initial defect. If probability parameter of the cyclic life period and delaminations growth are necessary then special methods of the histogram transformations may be used. Figure 9 shows initial data: histogram for nominal tensile stress σ , values of parameters in the crack growth equation n (constant) and C (histogram), probability density function $f(a_0)$ for length of initial delamination in the moment ($N = 0$) and moves of the function $f(a)$ in time. If it is adopted that critical length of the delamination a_c is equals to 0.1 M, than probability of the fact that length of the grown delamination exceeds a_c for 5×10^4 cycles is 0.14. Analogous results were obtained for all calculation cases.

Figure 9. Calculation of probability of fracture

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to prof. Machutov N.A., prof. Alumov V.T. and their colleagues, Institute of Machinery of the Russian Academy of Sciences, for help with the nondestructive evaluations and general support.

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